

PROBIOTIC SUPPLEMENTATION AS A STRATEGY FOR IMPROVEMENT IN BODY COMPOSITION, GROWTH, AND SURVIVAL OF PATHOGEN CHALLENGED LABEO ROHITA FINGERLINGS

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Abstract

The effectiveness of probiotic-enriched diets on the growth, survival, and body composition of *Labeo rohita* fingerlings challenged with *Pseudomonas fluorescens* was assessed in this study. The feed contained two probiotic strains viz *Bacillus aerius* AsCh-A7 and *Sphingomonas* sp. AsCh-P3 with antagonistic activity against fish pathogens. All experimental groups and the positive control (C2) received intraperitoneal injections of pathogen suspensions (O.D-0.5), whereas the negative control was fed a sterile diet and was not exposed to any pathogen. Fish were divided into six experimental groups: G2a, G2b, and G2c (for *B. aerius* AsCh-A7) and G1a, G1b, and G1c (for *Sphingomonas* sp. AsCh-P3). Probiotic supplementation regimes involved: 30 days feeding after exposure (G1a, G2a); 15 days pre-feeding followed by 30 days after-exposure (G1b, G2b); 15 days pre-exposure feeding (G1c, G2c). Muscle tissue samples were used to assess growth performance and biochemical composition after 45 days. All experimental groups showed improved average weight, weight gain, and specific growth rate (SGR) by both probiotics whereas the pre- and post-treated groups (G1b, G2b) had the highest survival rates (80–90%). The pathogen-exposed control (C2) showed a significant decrease in all biochemical components. With the exception of total protein, ash content, and RNA, *Sphingomonas* sp. AsCh-P3 supplementation had a substantial impact on the majority of biochemical contents. On the other hand, *B. aerius* AsCh-A7 supplementation markedly raised total lipids, carbs, RNA, and DNA in all treated groups whereas total protein dropped in G2a and G2b but not in G2c. *Sphingomonas* sp. AsCh-P3 and *Bacillus aerius* AsCh-A7 are excellent probiotic candidates for improving the health and resilience of freshwater fish under pathogenic stress.

INTRODUCTION

Aquaculture, one of the fastest-growing food production industries in the world, is essential to maintaining both global food security and nutritional sustainability. The increasing demand for animal protein in human diets is largely met by fish, a highly

digestible and protein-rich food source (FAO, 2024). Freshwater aquaculture, which provides a healthier source of vital amino acids, fatty acids, vitamins, and minerals, has grown significantly in popularity in many Asian nations as an economical and effective

substitute for the production of red meat (Naylor et al., 2021; Boyd et al., 2022). The need for sustainable methods to improve fish growth, survival, and health is highlighted by the growing reliance on aquaculture, especially in situations involving intense rearing and disease exposure.

Pathogen-related disease outbreaks are serious threat in aquaculture. This challenge may lead to substantial financial losses and driving risk at animal health. The intensification of antimicrobial-resistant (AMR) bacteria and exploitation of antibiotics in aquaculture are considered a major challenge for prevention of disease and health of animal (Cabello et al., 2022; FAO, 2023). Consequently, probiotics are considered as considerable promising candidates as environmental safe strategy for health promotion.

Ringo et al. (2020) and Nayak (2021) noted that probiotics are live bacterial inclusions and they assist the host by enhancing nutrient absorption, enhancing immunological response, and altering the flora of the gut under the right dosage. Kachamakova et al. (2006) have credited their use in the aquaculture industry as potent biocontrol agent in reducing pathogen colonization and enhancing the overall health of fish. As some of the probiotic strains have been effectively used as dietary feed supplement to enhance growth and resistance to diseases. Hence the addition of live beneficial inclusions may enhance the health of fish (Boonthai et al., 2011; Seenivasan et al., 2012). Some probiotic taxa, including *Bacillus*, *Lactobacillus*, *Carnobacterium*, and *Pseudomonas*, have demonstrated potential use in increasing the growth performance, feed consumption, and resistance to disease in a range of fish species (Verschuere et al., 2000; Chaudhary and Qazi, 2014; Zorriehzahra et al., 2020; Hoseinifar et al., 2023).

Evaluation of probiotics should be done on commercially effective species in the fresh water systems due to the promise of correcting the health and growth rate of the fish. One highly marketable carp, *labeo rohita* (rohu), is well-known due to its growth, white flesh of high quality, and high level of consumption (Hamilton et al., 2022). Rohu is an important part of the inland aquaculture in Pakistan and a good source of low-cost animal protein to the local population (Mohsin et al., 2017). Nevertheless, the intensification of rohu culture most often leads to the increased exposure to opportunistic infections

and variations in the environment, which can lead to a new disease outbreak and lowered productivity (Irshath et al., 2023). To enhance growth, feed consumption, immune resistance, and disease resistance in rohu under commercial farming conditions, such nutritional interventions as probiotic-supplemented diets are actively studied as a sustainable and antibiotic-free approach (Chaudhary and Qazi, 2007; Dawood and Koshio, 2016; Ghori et al., 2022).

The impact of probiotic-enriched diets in this research are considered to mitigate stress caused by pathogens and improve growth profile, survivability to exposure to pathogens, and body composition of *Labeo rohita* fingerlings. The present research study examined the impacts of two locally isolated probiotic strains *Sphingomonas* sp. AsCh-P3 and *Bacillus aerius* AsCh-A7, when challenged by *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, compared to no challenged fishes.

The comparative approach will provide innovative insights as a measure of screening probiotic activity and protection in freshwater fish (Dawood and Koshio, 2016; Hoseinifar et al., 2021). Also, proximate body composition such as protein, lipid, carbohydrate, ash and moisture contents were analyzed. Changes in these biochemical elements are known to influence fish rate of metabolism, food intake, and muscle deposition (Abdel-Tawwab et al., 2020; Ghori et al., 2022; Dawood et al., 2023). To enhance fish development, health and disease resilience of sustainable aquaculture systems, the outcomes of this study offer valuable information concerning the development of functional probiotic based feeds.

Materials and Methods

Fish Feed Formula (25% protein)

The rice polishing 34.3, fish meal 5.0, molasses 4.0, ground nut oil cake 53.7, table salt 1.0, dicalcium phosphate 1.0 and vitamin premix 1.0 were main components for feed formulation. *Bacillus aerius* AsCh-A7 and *Sphingomonas* sp. AsCh-P3 suspensions (10% v/w) containing 150×10^6 and 93×10^6 C.F.U/g respectively were added in fish feed. It was then dried under sterile conditions at room temperature ($\sim 27-30$ °C) over a period of 3 days and stored under refrigeration up to 7 days. Control feed lacks probiotic isolate (Chaudhary et al., 2021).

Source of Probiotic Isolates and Fish Pathogen

Pathogen *Pseudomonas fluorescens* was isolated from *Labeo rohita* that exhibited ulcerative disease and was collected from the research fish ponds (University of the Punjab, Lahore). In the pathogenicity trial, the isolated pathogen caused approximately 50% mortality when fingerlings were injected intraperitoneally with 2.68×10^3 CFU/mL (0.1 mL of bacterial suspension). Infected fish exhibited clinical symptoms including abdominal swelling, anal inflammation, reddening of the ventral surface, and scale erosion. Meanwhile, *Bacillus aerius* AsCh-A7 and *Sphingomonas* sp. AsCh-P3 (Accession No. MF543123, MF543125) were selected as probiotic candidates

based on their in vitro antibacterial activity against *Pseudomonas fluorescens* (Chaudhary et al., 2021).

Experimental Design

Labeo rohita fingerlings were acclimated for 10 days to laboratory conditions for the period of their arrival and experimental set up. During acclimatization period, fishes were examined for health and nutrition. Fishes were fed with designated feed (3% of fish body weight) once a day within the experimental period. Cleaning of glass aquaria was done once a day with change of two third water and maintained temperature was 24 to 27 °C.

Table 1: Experimental design for probiotic treatment and infection of the fish

Sr. No	Group/ Sub groups	Subgroups	Feeding (15 days)	i.p. injection (0.1 ml)	Feeding (30days)
1	Negative Control	C1	Feed without probiotics	PBS	Feed without probiotics
2	Positive Control	C2	Feed without probiotics	<i>P. fluorescens</i>	Feed without probiotics
3	<i>P. fluorescens</i> + <i>Sphingomonas</i> sp. AsCh-P3	G1a	Feed without probiotics	<i>P. fluorescens</i>	P3 treated feed
		G1b	P3 supplemented feed	<i>P. fluorescens</i>	P3 treated feed
		G1c	P3 supplemented feed	<i>P. fluorescens</i>	Feed without probiotics
4	<i>P. fluorescens</i> + <i>Bacillus aerius</i> AsCh-A7	G2a	Feed without probiotics	<i>P. fluorescens</i>	A7 treated feed
		G2b	A7 supplemented feed	<i>P. fluorescens</i>	A7 treated feed
		G2c	A7 supplemented feed	<i>P. fluorescens</i>	Feed without probiotics

The experimental data was collected in triplicates and each replicate contained 10 fish per aquarium. According to experimental design, all group received probiotic supplemented or without probiotic feed for 15 days. The designated experimental/positive control groups were exposed to *Pseudomonas fluorescens* suspension including 268×10^3 C.F.U/mL (0.1 mL) through intraperitoneal injections whereas 0.1 mL PBS (Phosphate buffer saline) was inoculated intraperitoneally to negative control (Table 1).

Study of growth factors

Mortality post pathogen exposure was noted down for positive and experimental groups while feeding with respective probiotic supplemented feed. Survival rate was computed after removal of dead fish. For calculation of growth factors viz average weight, specific growth rate and weight gain, live fish were weighed to collect data at different time intervals (start of experiment-Ri, pathogen inoculation-R0), post 15 days-R1, post 30 days-R2). The growth factors were calculated by following formula;

$$\text{Survival rate} = (\text{Survived fish} / \text{Stocked fish}) \times 100$$

SGR (specific growth rate)= [(log Wf-log Wi)/days] ×100

WG (g) = Wf (g) - Wi (g)

Where Wf, Wi were final weight and initial weight respectively

Biochemical constituents of Muscle tissue

For extraction of constituents viz DNA, RNA, protein, carbohydrate, lipids, of muscle (three fishes per replicate), homogenization technique was used (Shakoori and Ahmad, 1973; Anwar et al., 2004). Different protocols were used for measurement of biochemical constituents (Lowry et al., 1951; Dubois et al., 1956; Schnieder, 1957; Zollner and Kirsch, 1962). Furnace and oven was used for the measurement of ash and moisture contents following temperatures 550 °C and 105°C.

Analysis of experimental data using statistics

ANOVA with Dunkun’s multiple range test (SPSS ver.20.0 software, SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA was used as for the comparison of all experimental data to calculate the appropriateness of the group. All data was presented as means and standard error means of replicates.

Results

Growth Performance of Labeo rohita fingerlings

The *Pseudomonas fluorescens* challenged *Labeo rohita* fingerlings were administered with respective probiotic (*Sphingomonas sp.* AsCh-P3, *Bacillus aerius*

AsCh-A7) treated feed separately in different ways as; Group G1a and G2a were fed with treated feed soon after challenge for 30 days, Group G1b and G2b was provided with treated feed for 15 days pre and 30 days post challenge while group G1c and G2c got treated feed for 15 days prior and control feed (30 days) after challenge. Fish pathogen *Pseudomonas fluorescens* was introduced by *i-p* injection (0.1ml) to positive control fishes (C2) and all experimental fishes while each negative control fish (C1) received 0.1ml PBS. Disease was induced by pathogen and 50% fishes were survived in positive control. Probiotic isolate *Sphigomonas sp.* AsCh-P3 showed improvement (p<0.05) in fish survival such as Group G1a- 53.33%, G1b- 80% and G1c- 73.33% whereas 73.33% in G2a, 90% in G3b and 86.66% in G2c fishes were survived by incorporation of *Bacillus aerius* AsCh-A7 (**Table 1**). As growth factors were concerned, increment in specific growth rate, average weight, weight gain was recorded in *Labeo rohita* fingerlings receiving respective probiotic administered feed than control groups. In average weight, maximum increase was 4.14±0.79, 4.70±1.00 (G1b), 4.40±0.88, 5.12±0.96 (G2b) after 15 pre and 30 days post pathogen exposure. All experimental fishes followed similar trend in weight gain (G1b 0.56±0.23; G2b 0.72±0.14) and SGR G1a 2.03±0.62; G2b 1.05±0.23) after 30 days (**Table 2**).

Table 2: Growth Profile of pathogen exposed *L. rohita* fingerlings fed with respective probiotic feed

Aspects	Parameters	Groups for experiment							
		Negative control C1	Positive control C2	G1a	G1b	G1c	G2a	G2b	G2c
Morphometry	Initial average weight	At start of exp. 2.55±0.26	2.93±0.48	3.18±0.70	3.30±0.71	3.01±0.52	3.19±0.72	3.48±0.68	3.44±0.76
	Average weight	R0 (at time of injection) 2.71±0.32	3.13±0.52	3.36±0.74	3.80±0.78	3.54±0.57	3.36±0.71	4.13±0.79	3.83±0.84
		R1(15 days post injection) 3.04±0.42	3.49±0.47	3.87±0.85	4.14±0.79	3.19±0.62	4.06±0.80	4.40±0.88	4.12±0.85
		R2(30 days post injection) 3.53±0.30	3.94±0.44	4.42±1.02	4.70±1.00	4.33±0.79	4.58±0.89	5.12±0.96	4.76±1.08

Nutritional Indices

Weight gain (WG)	R0 (at time of injection)	a	ab	ab	c	c	ab	c	bc	
		0.16±0.07	0.20±0.06	0.19±0.04	0.50±0.09	0.53±0.06	0.17±0.01	0.65±0.02	0.39±0.08	
	R1(15 days post injection)	a	a	ab	a	a	b	a	a	
		0.34±0.11	0.37±0.04	0.51±0.01	0.34±0.02	0.37±0.04	0.70±0.09	0.27±0.02	0.29±0.03	
	R2(30 days post injection)		0.49±0.14	0.44±0.04	0.55±0.08	0.56±0.23	0.42±0.07	0.52±0.02	0.72±0.04	0.65±0.04
	Specific growth Rate (SGR)	R0 (at time of injection)	a	ab	ab	c	c	ab	c	bc
		0.38±0.14	0.48±0.03	0.38±0.01	0.95±0.11	1.11±0.01	0.37±0.00	1.15±0.09	0.73±0.04	
	R1 (15 days post injection)	a	ab	ab	ab	ab	b	c	ab	
		0.74±0.17	0.81±0.01	0.94±0.01	0.62±0.12	0.66±0.03	1.30±0.09	0.41±0.03	0.52±0.00	
R2 (30 days post injection)		1.08±0.41	0.83±0.06	2.03±0.02	0.79±0.18	0.62±0.06	0.81±0.04	1.05±0.03	0.93±0.04	
% Survival Rate (SR)	(30 days post injection)	a	b	b	c	c	c	a	ac	
	100±0.00	50±5.78	53.33±3.33	80±0.00	73.33±3.33	73.33±3.33	90±0.00	86.66±3.33		

The data is in form of mean and standard error mean of replicates. The significance was interpreted via not sharing common alphabet in respective row ($p \leq 0.05$).

C1 PBS 0.1 mL inoculation + sterilized feed

C2 Pathogen 0.1ml + sterilized feed

G1a, G2a Pathogen exposed fish + respective probiotic supplemented feed for 30 days

G1b, G2b 15 days probiotic feed + pathogen exposure + 30 day probiotic feed

G1c, G2c 15 days probiotic feed + pathogen exposure + 30 day sterilized feed

G1 (a-c) *Sphingomonas* sp. AsCh-P3 supplemented feed

G2 (a-c) *B. aerius* AsCh-A7 supplemented feed

Biochemical Constituents of Fish Muscle Tissue

The analysis of biochemical constituents was performed in pathogen exposed healthy fish sampled after 15 and 30 days (Table 3). A substantial ($p < 0.05$) decrease was observed in Total protein, DNA and ash in pathogen exposed control group-C2 at 30 days where as RNA and DNA levels were improved after 15 days.

The inoculation of *Sphingomonas* sp. AsCh-P3 soon after pathogen challenge (G1a) resulted in substantial increase in the level of all contents except total protein and ash contents ($p > 0.05$) after 15 days. A substantial increase was maintained in the level of lipids, moisture contents and RNA after probiotic supplementation when compared with control fishes

at experiment termination time. An abrupt decrease occurred in total protein and total carbohydrate contents in spite of probiotic supply after 30 days. The fishes subjected to *Bacillus aerius* AsCh-A7 (G2a) showed a substantial increase in the level of Total carbohydrate, moisture contents, RNA and decrease ($p < 0.05$) in values of Total protein and Total lipids after 30 days as comparable with control group (C1). After 15 days, Total carbohydrate, glucose, moisture, RNA, DNA contents were different considerably ($p < 0.05$) than control while absolute decrease was evident in Total protein and Total lipids.

The comparison of G1b fishes, supplemented with probiotic before and after pathogen challenge with control fishes showed absolute enhanced values of

carbohydrates and lipid contents while absolute decrease was apparent in the values of Total protein, RNA and DNA after 30 days. Substantial ($p < 0.05$) variations in all contents were observed after 15 days with increase in lipids and decrease in ash, RNA and DNA contents. In G2b, a substantial ($p < 0.05$) decrease in Total protein while carbohydrate, lipid and moisture contents were increased considerably ($p < 0.05$) than control fishes at experimental termination time. A substantial ($p < 0.05$) decrease in Total protein, ash and RNA values with increase in Total lipids were evident after 15 days to control fishes.

Total lipids and DNA contents were enhanced considerably ($p < 0.05$) among the fishes subjected to

Sphingomonas sp. AsCh-P3 prior pathogen challenge (G1c) while the values of ash and RNA contents were depressed at experiment termination time. After 15 days, Total carbohydrates and RNA contents differ considerably ($p < 0.05$) from control fishes. The values of Total protein, ash and DNA contents were decreased substantially ($p < 0.05$). In G2c, increase in the values of Total protein, ash, lipids, moisture and DNA contents was observed after 30 days. Substantial ($p < 0.05$) variation in all body contents was observed after 15 days with increase in Total carbohydrates, Total lipids, moisture and DNA contents.

Table 3: Profile of biochemical constituents of pathogen exposed *L. rohita* fingerlings fed with respective probiotic feed

Biochemical constituents		Negative control		Positive control		Groups of experiment			
		C1	C2	G1a	G1b	G1c	G2a	G2b	G2c
Total Protein	R1(15 days post injection)	a 26.29±0.40	b 23.21±0.50	b 23.71±0.45	b 23.83±0.59	a 25.37±0.16	c 25.30±0.12	c 24.87±0.21	c 24.66±0.31
	R2(30 days post injection)	a 26.21±0.28	b 24.20±0.61	c 24.70±0.37	cd 24.32±0.55	ad 25.13±0.44	c 22.44±0.51	b 24.45±0.28	d 29.87±0.56
Total Carbohydrates	R1(15 days post injection)	a 23.88±2.00	a 21.54±1.11	b 53.23±2.72	c 27.90±2.73	c 26.27±0.49	b 23.16±2.11	a 24.97±3.01	c 46.78±2.77
	R2(30 days post injection)	a 26.37±1.04	a 29.54±0.99	b 12.09±0.64	c 44.43±1.67	d 34.44±0.72	b 84.52±5.87	c 34.68±2.04	ac 27.75±1.15
Total Lipids	R1(15 days post injection)	a 244.98±11.77	b 215.40±3.05	a 246.67±2.68	c 301.37±6.18	c 310.52±2.45	b 217.93±2.55	c 290.56±9.38	d 266.51±4.78
	R2(30 days post injection)	a 210.78±4.39	b 265.38±4.02	b 253.43±4.68	c 307.36±9.07	d 332.95±6.48	c 164.45±1.56	d 343.98±2.35	e 321.86±4.43
DNA	R1(15 days post injection)	a 0.71±0.09	b 1.04±0.05	a 0.75±0.05	c 0.29±0.04	d 0.12±0.02	b 0.92±0.05	a 0.57±0.04	c 1.63±0.03
	R2(30 days post injection)	a 1.03±0.07	b 0.62±0.09	a 1.02±0.04	c 0.30±0.06	d 1.24±0.04	a 1.15±0.06	a 1.04±0.06	c 1.58±0.04

RNA	R1(15 days post injection)	a 4.40±0.0 3	b 5.80±0.07	b 5.57±0.0 5	c 3.79±0.0 7	c 4.65±0.0 2	b 5.69±0.0 6	c 4.01±0.0 2	c 4.01±0.0 2
	R2(30 days post injection)	a 4.21±0.0 5	b 5.30±0.19	c 5.49±0.0 2	d 3.87±0.0 6	d 4.06±0.0 4	b 5.41±0.1 2	a 4.09±0.0 2	a 4.02±0.0 3
Ash contents	R1(15 days post injection)	a 13.15±0. 20	b 11.61±0.2 5	b 11.85±0. 23	b 11.91±0. 30	c 12.68±0. 08	c 12.65±0. 06	c 12.44±0. 10	c 12.33±0. 16
	R2(30 days post injection)	a 13.10±0. 14	b 12.10±0.3 0	c 12.35±0. 18	cd 12.16±0. 27	ad 12.57±0. 22	c 11.22±0. 26	b 12.22±0. 14	d 14.94±0. 28
Moisture contents	R1(15 days post injection)	a 68.02±2. 53	b 78.74±2.5 3	b 83.24±3. 07	a 66.45±2. 77	ab 75.25±2. 27	c 93.37±4. 49	ab 73.88±2. 27	b 79.95±4. 50
	R2(30 days post injection)	a 69.53±2. 02	b 93.97±1.9 8	c 101.05±3 .22	a 66.80±1. 94	a 70.59±1. 78	b 97.05±1. 96	d 85.64±2. 46	d 83.03±5. 57

The data is in form of mean and standard error mean of replicates. The significance was interpreted via not sharing common alphabet in respective row ($p \leq 0.05$).

C1 PBS 0.1 mL inoculation + sterilized feed

C2 Pathogen 0.1ml + sterilized feed

G1a, G2a Pathogen exposed fish + respective probiotic supplemented feed for 30 days

G1b, G2b 15 days probiotic feed + pathogen exposure + 30 day probiotic feed

G1c, G2c 15 days probiotic feed + pathogen exposure + 30 day sterilized feed

G1 (a-c) *Sphingomonas* sp. AsCh-P3 supplemented feed

G2 (a-c) *B. aerius* AsCh-A7 supplemented feed

Discussion

One of Pakistan's most significant commercial carp species is *Labeo rohita*, which is high quality for its tasty flavor, strong market demand, and remarkable nutritional contents. Since balanced nutrition directly affects fish growth, health, and survival, effective feeding management strategies is essential to the success of aquaculture production. Addition of live microorganisms to aquafeeds improves digestive efficiency and nutrient absorption. It also promotes overall fish health (Panigrahi et al., 2005; Abo-State et al., 2009). In the current investigation, *L. rohita* fingerlings challenged with *Pseudomonas fluorescens* were given feed supplemented with *Sphingomonas* sp. AsCh-P3 and *Bacillus aerius* AsCh-A7. According to the results of Authira et al. (2011), the probiotics were introduced using a spray-drying technique, which helped preserve their viability and stability in the diet.

Survival rates were recorded 80% and 90% when *Sphingomonas* sp. AsCh-P3 and *Bacillus aerius* AsCh-A7 were added to the food before and after pathogen exposure (G1b and G2b groups) respectively. These results explicitly showed that probiotic supplementation is effective in preventing *Pseudomonas fluorescens* infection. Probiotic-fed groups showed considerably reduced mortality than the pathogen-challenged control, which is consistent with previous results (Gatesoupe, 2002; Gatlin and Li, 2004). Numerous microorganisms, such as yeasts, unicellular algae, and both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, have been demonstrated in earlier research to be useful probiotics in aquaculture systems (Irianto and Austin, 2002). Because they are non-pathogenic to aquatic organisms (Moriarty, 1998), may produce antimicrobial chemicals, amino acids, and digestive enzymes (Sanders et al., 2003), and are

commonly used in commercial aquafeeds. *Bacillus* species are high-quality for their safety, stability, and functional advantages (Gullian et al., 2004).

In the current study, probiotic-treated groups shown significant improvements in all growth metrics, while pathogen delivery in the positive control group resulted in significant decreases in average weight, weight gain, and specific growth rate. *Bacillus* supplementation has been shown to have similar growth-promoting benefits in a number of fish species. Bairagi et al. (2004) found that common carp fed *B. aerius* and *B. circulans* had higher ultimate body weight and SGR. However, Kumar et al. (2006) found that oral *B. aerius* administration enhanced immunity in *Labeo rohita*. Similar results were also reported by studies demonstrating the advantageous function of probiotics based on *Bacillus* in enhancing fish health and disease resistance (Bagheri et al. 2008; Boonthai et al. 2011; Parthasarathy and Ravi, 2011).

Pseudomonas fluorescens infection clearly affected the biochemical composition of *Labeo rohita* in the pathogen-challenged control group (C2), which showed about 50% mortality along with a significant decrease in total protein, ash, and DNA contents as well as increased moisture levels. These changes in body composition are probably caused by metabolic disorders and physiological stress brought on by pathogenic infection. Fish exposed to bacterial diseases have been shown to exhibit similar decreases in protein and other macronutrients under disease stress (Ali et al., 2001; Abdel-Tawwab et al., 2006).

The biochemical indices for the probiotic-fed groups showed a marked improvement, which indicates a positive effect of *Sphingomonas* sp. AsCh-P3 and *Bacillus aerius* AsCh-A7 on the fish's metabolic rate and the ability of the fish to use nutrients. The G1a group (*Sphingomonas* sp. AsCh-P3) had significantly higher levels of total lipids and RNA than the control group, while G2a (*B. aerius* AsCh-A7) had higher levels of total carbohydrates and RNA than the control group. Although both groups had lower levels of total protein and ash than the control group, these reductions did not have a negative effect, and probably represent the use of protein to produce increased metabolic activity and to assist in the immune response. The higher levels of moisture for probiotic-fed fish may also be linked to a better osmoregulatory balance during times of stress.

Supporting studies showing similar conclusions was presented by Alizadeh et al. (2011) who stated that when fed with probiotics fish had a lower percentage of body fat because of higher levels of increased lipid metabolism to meet growth and energy needs. Hidalgo et al. (2006), and El Haroun et al. (2006) did not find any significant differences in total body protein concentrations with inclusion of probiotics whereas Eid and Mohamed (2008) observed similar results with fingerling samples of *Oreochromis niloticus* fed with standard commercial dietary supplements. Collectively, these data provide evidence that the use of probiotics supported metabolic stability and biochemical constituents in fish during exposure to pathogenic challenges.

Administering probiotics before and after exposure to pathogens in the G1b and G2b groups led to noticeable changes in body composition when compared to the control group. Probiotic receiving fish experienced substantial increases in carbohydrates and lipids. Contrary to improvement, declined muscle contents i.e., ash, protein, and RNA were recorded at termination of experiment. Krishnaveni et al. (2013) correlated the declined RNA with higher lipid with transferal metabolic mechanisms to lipid utilization. Lipid accumulation in fish muscle was also observed by Aubin et al. (2005) by addition of yeast and probiotics in feeds. This is the reflection of better metabolic efficiency and energy storage.

Pre challenge probiotic feeding (G1c, G2c) resulted in improved DNA, lipid along with raised ash, carbohydrates and protein in group G2c. Positive body changes in fish receiving respective probiotics reflected the efficacy of both probiotics. Group G1c exhibited the declined RNA that might be due to weak cellular turnover under stable conditions. The higher DNA levels in both groups (G1c, G2c) might be due to enhanced growth potential and cell proliferation and corroborated with the findings of Khan and Jafri (1991). Biogen and Pronifer supplemented feeds showed a positive growth and protein contents in *Oreochromis niloticus* (Eid and Mohamed, 2008). Additionally, Spirulina and yeast based feeding resulted in better nutrient retention and body compositional contents (Lara Flores et al., 2003; Abdel Tawwab et al., 2008). These findings confirmed the current outcomes of probiotic

inclusion by effective metabolic mechanisms to regulating energy and promoting biochemical profile in pathogen exposed *Labeo rohita*.

The physiological changes in the biochemical profile of fish in this study can also be explained by the stress, induced metabolic shift. According to Gobinath and Ramanibai (2013), the exposure to stress causes the consumption of carbohydrates that are the primary source of energy during the first stage of the stress response. When lipids are mobilized and exhausted, fish start breaking down their muscle proteins for energy. This change in the catabolic pathway increases the amount of water in muscles, which in turn raises the moisture content. The inverse relationship between muscle moisture and the levels of lipids and proteins in fish under stress has been established (Love, 1980; Shimma & Sato, 1985; Mahboob & Sheri, 1997). The current findings provides the stress based evidence that pathogen exposed fish (control group) have high moisture with declined lipid and protein contents in muscle. While respective probiotic feeding group displayed balanced body composition representing better physiological role, energy regulation and stress management.

Conclusion

The conclusion of the study defines the preventive role of probiotics as safe viable microbes to substitute antibiotics and disease resilience. The probiotic feeding regimes with *Bacillus aerius* AsChA7 and *Sphingomonas* sp. AsCh P3 harnesses the improved profiles of growth and proximate body composition in *Labeo rohita* fingerlings exposed to *Pseudomonas fluorescens*. The therapeutic attributes of probiotics feeding regimes improved the lipid and DNA level whereas pathogen stress decline the RNA and protein of fish muscle. Hence probiotics contributes to disease resilience by improving fish health and developing aquaculture to a remarkable position.

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